

Three New Nothogenera for Hybrids Between *Leuenbergeria*, *Pereskia* and *Rhodocactus* and a New Combination in *Rhodocactus* (Cactaceae: Leuenbergerioideae, Pereskioideae)

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Abstract—The new combination *Rhodocactus bahiensis* subsp. *minensis* (\equiv *Pereskia bahiensis* subsp. *minensis*) and the nothogenera \times *Rhodenbergeria* (*Rhodocactus* \times *Leuenbergeria*), \times *Perenbergeria* (*Leuenbergeria* \times *Pereskia*) and \times *Rhodeskia* (*Rhodocactus* \times *Pereskia*) are proposed.

Leuenberger (Mem. New York Bot. Gard. 41: 50-51. 1986) reports the existence of six interspecific hybrids between species included by him in *Pereskia* Mill. The segregation of *Leuenbergeria* Lodé ([Cact.-Avent. Int. 97: 26. 2012](#)) and *Rhodocactus* (A.Berger) F.M.Knuth ([Asai & Miyata, J. Jap. Bot. 91\(1\): 9. 2016](#)) from *Pereskia* has rendered three of these hybrids intergeneric. The appropriate nothogenera are proposed here:

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×*Rhodenbergeria* M.H.J.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.** = *Leuenbergeria* Lodé (Leuenbergerioideae) × *Rhodocactus* (A.Berger) F.M.Knuth (Pereskioideae). Based on *Leuenbergeria bleo* (Kunth) Lodé × *Rhodocactus grandifolius* (Haw.) F.M.Knuth (Leuenberger, Mem. New York Bot. Gard. 41: 50. 1986).

×*Perenbergeria* M.H.J.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.** = *Leuenbergeria* Lodé (Leuenbergerioideae) × *Pereskia* Mill. (Pereskioideae). Based on *Leuenbergeria bleo* (Kunth) Lodé × *Pereskia diaz-romeroana* Cárdenas (Leuenberger, Mem. New York Bot. Gard. 41: 50. 1986).

×*Rhodeskia* M.H.J.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.** = *Pereskia* Mill. (Pereskioideae) × *Rhodocactus* (A.Berger) F.M.Knuth (Pereskioideae). Based on *Pereskia diaz-romeroana* Cárdenas × *Rhodocactus nemorosus* (Rojas Acosta) Iss.Asai & K.Miyata (Leuenberger, Mem. New York Bot. Gard. 41: 50. 1986).

If the subfamily Leuenbergerioideae is accepted, the nothogenera ×*Rhodenbergeria* and ×*Perenbergeria* represent intersubfamilial hybrids. The only other intersubfamilial cactus hybrids reported in the literature are between Cactoideae and Opuntioideae (×*Disuntia* M.H.J.van der Meer = *Disocactus* Lindl. × *Opuntia* (L.) Mill.) and ×*Opuntara* M.H.J.van der Meer = *Disocactus* Lindl. × *Opuntia* (L.) Mill. × *Selenicereus* (A.Berger) Britton & Rose) ([van der Meer, Cact. Phantast. 1\(1\): 6. 2018](#)).

Additionally, the following new combination is proposed:

Rhodocactus bahiensis subsp. *minensis* (N.P.Taylor & Albuq.-Lima) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. nov.** ≡ *Pereskia bahiensis* subsp. *minensis* N.P.Taylor & Albuq.-Lima, Phytotaxa 494(3): 290 (2021).

